

PRODUCTION OF METAL FIBER BY COILED SHEET SLICING
METHOD AND ITS COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

A new manufacturing process of long-length metal fiber which can be applied to the composite materials has been developed. In this new process, the metal fiber is produced out of coiled thin metallic sheet by a new slicing method. In the manufacturing trial, each specific cutting conditions for fiber production from brass and either copper or stainless steel has been confirmed. This method has high productivity and applicability for many kind of materials. Then, the metal fiber obtained this method can be used for various fields of composite materials.

As one of the important characteristics of this method, it is capable that a uniformly mixed different material fibers can be easily produced with different material sheets such as metal, plastics and paper and so on, which are wound layer by layer. Using a uniformly mixed fiber of plastics and metals, the plastic pellet and sheet including metal fiber has been produced. Further, the electric conductive composite materials has been developed utilizing the plastic pellets and sheets.

KEYWORDS: Fiber/Metallic; Manufacturing; Fiber production; Fiber composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal fiber is used in many applications which utilize its characteristics possessing electrical conductivity, thermal conductivity, sintering properties, etc. inherent to metal, as well as in reinforcing application.

In recent year, a demand for metal fibers has increased as a basic mixing fiber for composite material with function like electrical conductivity etc. and as a mixing fiber for friction material in disc brake pad automobiles. Production method of metal fibers are drawing method, meltspinning method, machining method and others^{1) . 2) . 3) . 4)} but a more efficient and economical production method is needed to be developed.

The authors have developed a coiled sheet slicing method in which metal fiber is obtained by lathe turning thin metal sheet wound into a coil. Although the method can not produce fiber with strength as high as several times base material, it has advantages including adaptability to various kind of materials, easiness in getting fine fibers and others, also provides metal fiber producing method of low cost coming from machining process, and is considered to have several advantages as a producing method of fiber for mixing in functional composite materials.

Further, an important characteristics of the process is the ability of obtaining metal fiber bundles with different materials mixed uniformly, by winding different materials layer by layer and by slicing them. The different materials can include not only different kinds of metals but also plastic sheet, for example. Of these mixed fibers, the former can be used as a base material for fiber metallurgy, and the latter as a material for plastic pellet with metal fibers mixed.

The present report describes the relationship between the condition of fiber production and the properties of fibers produced in cases of applying this fiber producing method mainly to brass, copper and stainless steel, the production of mixed fibers by way of slicing laminated coil made of different materials, and further the production of composite materials by use of the process.

2. PRODUCTION EQUIPMENT FOR METAL FIBERS AND THE METHOD OF PRODUCTION EXPERIMENT

The schematic production method for metal fibers is shown in Fig. 1. The method consists of mounting thin sheet of metal on a raw material winding equipment, winding a proper amount of material nearly equal to the width of the cutter (for example 25 mm) on the spindle, lathe machining the edge face of the coil of thin metal, and obtaining metal fibers in bundles, each made of about 200 to 500 fibers.

When different materials are to be wound in lamination to produce fibers, as one of the special features of the process, the winding of thin metal sheet on spindle was done as shown in Fig. 2. Machining experiments were conducted according to the conditions shown in Table 1. Production

FIGURE 1. Schematic of coiled sheet slicing method

FIGURE 2. Winding method of different materials sheets

TABLE 1. Experiments conditions

Cutting tool	High speed tool steel Sintered carbide tool
Rake angle	10-45 degree
Feed rate	5-43 $\mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$
Cutting speed	37-86 m/min
Machining method	With cutting fluid Without cutting fluid

experiment of fibers were made without cutting fluid for brass and copper, and with cutting fluid for stainless steel. Produce metal fibers were examined with respect to their surface and cross sections by SEM, and tensile strength in universal testing machine (Shinkoh Tsusin Industry, Model TCM/200). Cross-sectional areas of fibers were measured from SEM photographs of cross sections, and the value converted to round section was made to be the equivalent diameter of the fibers.

3. PRODUCTION OF BRASS AND COPPER FIBERS

3.1 Region for formation of fibers In order to examine the appropriate condition for production, confirmations were made as to what kind of fibers were produced according to various machining conditions. In this experiment, approach angle of 2° cutting width of 10 mm and rake angle of 38° for

brass and 35° for copper were used, and the feed rate was varied in 5 to $30 \mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$. The state of fibers thus obtained is summarized according to machining conditions in Fig. 3 and 4. The state of obtained fibers is of short chip with curls and of powder-like chips instead of continuous fibers when the feed rate is small and cutting speed is small, and is of being fusion stucked by welding to each others in the direction of sheet thickness in coil when the feed rate is large and the cutting speed is large, becoming similar to chips in ordinary machining. Compared to brass, copper has wider region of conditions where fusion sticking occurs, but contrarily becomes

FIGURE 3. The classified of fiber formation region (brass) (Sheet thickness $t=0.1 \text{ mm}$)

FIGURE 4. The classified copper fiber appearance for each varying cutting condition (Sheet thickness $t=0.1 \text{ mm}$)

capable of producing fibers in low feed rate region. And, with maintenance of sharpness in the cutting edge of tool and with improvement in the rigidity of the machine, both materials are considered to become capable of producing fibers even in smaller feed rate.

3.2 Influence of rake angle

Selection of appropriate rake angle is considered to be an important point in getting good fibers. Here, the effect of rake angle on the state of fiber produced was examined. With the cutting width of 20 mm and back clearance angle of 10° being constant. The wedge angle of the tool was varied to get rake angle of 20° to 40° . The feed rate was $20 \mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$, and the cutting speed was 73 m/min. The experimental results are shown in Table 2. With smaller rake angle, a mix of normal fibers and stucked fiber with curls were formed. This is considered to be caused by an increase in cutting resistance arising from too small rake angle, and from accompanying evolution of heat caused by cutting resistance. With rake angle of 35° and 38° , the formation of flexible long fibers was

confirmed. And, in case of 40° in rake angle, the machining caused chatter vibration, and the formation of long fibers was impossible.

TABLE 2. The influence of rake angle in fiber formation

Cutting speed 73 m/min, Feed rate
20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$, Cutting width 20 mm

Rake angle (degree)	The state of fiber formation
20	Curled fibers
25	Fusion sticking fibers
30	Good fibers
35	Very good fibers
38	Very good fibers
40	No fibers

3.3 Fiber diameter A cross section of fibers exhibits rectangular, since the edge face of thin sheet is slicing. One side of the rectangular corresponds to the sheet thickness of the coil, and the other side is determined by the feed rate of the tool. Here, how the cross section of fibers changes according to the feed rate was investigated. The machining conditions were the feed rate of $20\mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$, cutting width of 20 mm, cutting speed of 82 m/min, and rake angle of 38° for brass and 35° for copper. The shape of fibers cross section is shown in Fig. 5. The equivalent diameter of fibers, and the ratio of increase in fiber thickness to the feed rate are shown in Table 3. At coil sheet thickness $t = 0.05$ mm, brass and copper had the equivalent diameter of $d = 48\mu\text{m}$ and $d = 57.6\mu\text{m}$ respectively, and at $t = 0.1$ mm, the equivalent diameter of $d = 71\mu\text{m}$ and $d = 84.3\mu\text{m}$ respectively, and the ratio of the increase in fiber thickness to the feed rate was 1.75, 1.95, 2.40 and 2.75 respectively.

Feed rate 20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$, Cutting
speed 82 m/min, Cutting width 20 mm
Sheet thickness $t=0.05$ mm

FIGURE 5. The cross section of copper fibers

Table 3. The equivalent diameter of fibers and the ratio of increase in fiber thickness to the feed rate

	Sheet thickness (mm)	Equivalent diameter (μm)	Ratio of increase in fiber thickness
Brass	0.05	48	1.75
	0.1	71	1.95
Copper	0.05	57.6	2.40
	0.1	84.3	2.75

3.4 Fiber strength Tensile strength test results for brass and copper fibers produced with coil sheet thickness of $t = 0.1$ mm are shown in Fig. 6 and 7. Neither metal fibers show clearly the effect of cutting speed on their tensile strength, but the feed rate has shown to increase the strength with its increase. This is considered to be due to smaller influence of surface defects in fibers such as notches with increase in fiber diameter according to the increase in the feed rate. And, fiber strength of brass was generally larger than the base material (421 MPa), and, on the other hand, that of copper did not show such an increase (base strength 216 MPa).

FIGURE 6. Tensile strength of brass fibers
Sheet thickness $t=0.1$ mm

FIGURE 7. Tensile strength of copper fibers
Sheet thickness $t=0.1$ mm

4. PRODUCTION OF MIXED FIBERS

4.1 Fiber production experiment Conducting the producing experiments of mixed fibers by way of lamination of plastic and metal, the condition for obtaining good fibers both with respect to metal and plastic, which should have different appropriate conditions of slicing, was investigated. In a set of SUS304 and PP (polypropylene sheet), a smaller rake angle of 15° at the same feed rate makes no fiber of pp, but short chips with curls or powder-like chips. On the other hand, at larger rake angle of 32° , pp forms

fusion sticks, making no good fibers, and therefore no good mixed fibers. At the rake angle of 25° , good fibers of SUS304 and pp were obtained. Compared to metal fibers sliced solely from metal, however, the SUS304 fibers in this case were plenty of curled ones. At the rake angle of 25° were good mixed fibers were obtained, the tool life at cutting edge of the tool was about 40 min after grinding. In the lamination of brass and plastic, it was confirmed that good fibers were obtained with cutting condition nearly equal to the ones for brass. Table 4 summarizes the equivalent diameter of fibers mixed with the plastic, the ratio of their increase, and their strength. An

Table 4. Summarizes the equivalent diameters of metal fiber mixed with plastic the ratio of the increase in fiber thickness and the tensile strength

	Feed rate ($\mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$)	Equivalent diameter (μm)	Increase ratio	Tensile strength (MPa)
PP + SUS 304	29	87.8	1.72	981
PP + Brass	21	75.2	1.84	477

elongation to the direction of sheet thickness is seen in both brass and SUS304, and its extent is about 1.2 times. And the fiber strength was as high as the strength of the base material, or was small larger than that.

5. PRODUCTION OF VARIOUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS

5.1 A production of plastic pellets mixed with metal fibers by use of mixed fibers

Using plastic mixed fibers obtained by the coiled sheet slicing method, a production of metal fiber mixed pellets was tried. The production method for metal fiber mixed pellets is shown in Fig. 8. Plastic mixed fibers as obtained from the coiled sheet slicing method were passed through

FIGURE 8. The production method for composite pellets mixed with metal fiber

a heater heated to about 300°C to make the plastic fibers to be fused, and to envelope metal fibers with plastic, and then formed in dies to obtain a long plastic mixed with fibers after cooling it. It was then cut into an appropriate length by a cutter to obtain metal fiber mixed pellets. Thus produced metal fiber mixed plastic pellets are shown in Fig. 9. The method has an advantage of obtaining plastic pellets by the same process as the production of fibers.

FIGURE 9. Appearance of plastic pellets mixed with metal fiber

5.2 Unwoven material for electromagnetic interference(EMI) shield Unwoven shield material is expected to provide material of good EMI shield with small content of fibers. As a production method of unwoven shield material, a process including cutting of plastic mixed metal fibers, uniform lamination of them, and then forming with compression molding at elevated temperature, can be employed to obtain the sheet, but in the present experiment, brass fibers with equivalent diameter of about 40 μ m were cut into 4 to 5 cm,

FIGURE 10. A convenient measuring method of EMI shielding effect

laminated so as to have a predetermined content of fibers, and formed, sandwiching it between 0.3 mm sheet of PVC, with compression molding at about 170°C to obtain a metal fiber composite plate of 150 x 150 x 1 mm. A convenient measuring method of EMI shield, and its EMI shielding effect are shown in Fig. 10 and 11, respectively. With small content of 150 gr/m² fibers, a shielding effect larger than 30 dB is shown at frequency region of 100 to 1000 MHz.

FIGURE 11. EMI shielding effectiveness of unwoven material with brass fiber content of 150 gr/m² (Fiber length 4 to 5 cm, equivalent diameter of about 40 μm)

5.3 Injection molding by use of metal fiber mixed pellets Using the method similar to the plastic polymer enveloping method of electric wire extrusion of fine wire from the mix of metal fibers and plastic by extrusion machine, and then cutting of it into 6 mm length were made to produce metal

FIGURE 12. Composite pellets mixed with metal fiber by use of the extrusion method

fiber mixed pellets. The metal fiber mixed pellets thus produced are shown in Fig. 12. Further, mixing with pellets containing only plastic in order to obtain a predetermined content of fibers, a plate of 150 x 150x3mm was formed by injection molding. The composite plate with 15 vol.% of metal fibers has the EMI shielding effect shown in Fig. 13.

FIGURE 13. EMI shielding effectiveness of the composite plate with 15 vol.% of brass fibers (A plate of 150x150x3 mm was produced by injection molding)

6. CONCLUSIONS

Examining a method of producing metal fibers by slicing of thin sheets of metal, conditions for obtaining good fibers of brass, copper and stainless steel were confirmed. And production methods for several composite materials containing the metal fibers made thereby were examined.

[References]

1. S.Kohda et al.: Production of Metal Fibers and Its Application, Metal 50 (1980), No.5, pp.2-22
2. A.Yanagisawa, M.Kaneko and M.Sugimoto: Production of Metal Fiber with Coiled Sheet Slicing, 13th Symposium on JSCM (1988), pp.139-142
3. A.Yanagisawa, M.Kaneko and M.Sugimoto: Production of Several Kind of Metal Fiber by Coiled Sheet Slicing Method, JSPE (Spring,1989),pp.443-444
4. A.Yanagisawa, M.Kaneko, M.Higuchi and M.Sugimoto: Production of Stainless Steel Fiber by Coiled Sheet Slicing Method, JSPE (Spring,1990), pp.81-82